

**ADVANCED COMPOSITE TECHNOLOGY
OF WEST GERMAN GENERAL AVIATION AIRCRAFT**

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INTRODUCTION

Several West German aircraft companies (C.D. Seastar, Gyroflug, Grob) have developed single and twin-engined small aircraft for general aviation in the FAR Part 23 certification category. These aircraft are built entirely of composite materials. The basis for the design and production methods were derived from the West German glider industry. The West German glider industry has been building gliders entirely of composite materials for 30 years very successfully. More than 12.000 gliders have been sold world-wide which have flown more than 3.2 billion kilometers and about 30 million flight hours in all possible climatic conditions. The applicability of the composite design for gliders has been proven convincingly by this wealth of experience.

The above-mentioned powered aircraft manufacturers have used this experience and used the glider technology for the development of their aircraft. Due to the differences between a glider and powered aircraft in design, loading and performance in service, additional developments and qualification are necessary of powered aircraft. To close the existing gaps, comprehensive technological investigations and project developments have been carried out. The following sections give an overview of the aircraft projects concerned, the content of the technological programmes and some results from these programmes.

GERMAN GENERAL AVIATION AIRCRAFT

The most important aircraft projects under development or in operation are the following:

Grob G115

Max. T.- O. weight 900 kg

GROB G 115

SPEED CANARD SC 01

**Gyroflug
Speed Canard**

Max. T.- O. weight 680 kg

Seastar CD 02

Max. T.- 0. weight 4600 kg

FIG 1 West German general aviation aircraft

DESCRIPTION OF COMPOSITE MANUFACTURING METHODS (LPC-TECHNOLOGY)

The West German small aircraft industry applies low pressure composite technology, in contrast to the generally known high pressure used composite technology.

Figure 2 shows a comparison of the two technologies

HPC (high pressure cured composites)

- 1/2 Two high strength upper and lower negative molds (alternatively vacuum bag may replace mold 1, depending on size and surface specs)
- 3 Preimpregnated (PREPREG) fiber/epoxy resin sheets
- 4 Heat and pressure resistant honeycomb core
- 5 High pressure force
- 6 High curing temperature
- 7 Autoclave

HPC is manufactured from semi-cured prepreg sheets incorporating fibers and the matrix material (resin). The final chemical compound is achieved by application of high pressure and temperature in a special autoclave.

LPC (low pressure cured composites)

- 1 Single negative mold of simple construction
- 2 fiber fabric sheets laminated with epoxy resin wet
- 3 Light, easily adaptable sandwich core
- 4 Vacuum foil
- 5 Ambient pressure
- 6 Suction pump manifold
- 7 Low curing temperature
- 8 Seal

The LPC compound is attained by laminating fiber fabrics and epoxy resing wet under low atmospheric pressure and medium heat. Curing of large airframe Section at 80° to 90°C is accomplished outside the mold.

FIG 2 Comparison of composite construction / manufacturing methods

The advantages of the LPC technology are the low manufacturing costs due to the low expenditure for the manufacturing equipment. The cure temperature for the LPC technology is 80 - 90° degrees Celsius, whereas, for the HPC technology, the components are cured at high pressure in an autoclave. The LPC technology is therefore particularly practical and easy production technique, which requires only low investments, for small aircraft companies.

TECHNOLOGY PROGRAMM FOR VERIFICATION OF LPC COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

The principal procedure for verification of LPC composite structures is shown in the following chart:

FIG 3 Chart of Technology Program for Verification of LPC Composite Structure

The following section gives an overview of the most important investigations and results of the

Component Tests

- a. Fuselage Frame

Structural Part Tests

- a. Speed Canard Wing
- b. G115 Wing

It is not possible, in this presentation to go into detail on

- a. Standard Wing Spar Component (I - Section and [] - Section)
- b. Seastar Wing
- c. Seastar Horizontal Tail
- d. Seastar Fuselage

due to the extent of the information.

RESULTS

4. Material and Design Verification by Component Tests

A. Fuselage Frame

- a. Design and Materials

FIG 4 Fuselage Frame Component

b. Test Description

This series of tests was intended to determine the influence of environmental conditions (temperature, humidity) on the strength behaviour, in addition to the static strength and fatigue life.

Static Tests

- o RT / dry
- o RT / wet
- o 72 °C / dry
- o 72 °C / wet

Fatigue Tests

- o RT / dry
- o RT / wet
- o temperature cycles / dry
- o temperature cycles / wet

C. Results

5. Material and Design Verification by Structural Part Test

A. Speed Canard Wing

a. Test Description

This test served to determine the static strength, the fatigue life, the residual strength and the damage tolerance behaviour. A total of 25 service damages and manufacturing defects were tested under static and fatigue loading. FIG 5 shows schematically the types of damage investigated and test set-up.

The following test sequence were carried out:

- manufacturing defects and impact damages inflicted
- fatigue test up to limit load at RT and 72 °C
- fatigue test for one life (12.000 flight hours) with a random test program (142 load cycles per flight hour) at RT; all loads of the fatigue program are factored by 1.1
- static test up to limit load at RT and 72 °C
- repair of one additional large visible damage
- static test up to ultimate load at RT and 72 °C
- fatigue test for two further lives (total 36.000 flight hours)
- conditioning of the wing at 45 °C/85% relative humidity for 2100 hours)
- static test up to ultimate load at 72 °C
- static strength test up to failure at 72 °C (additional fail safe and damage tolerance investigations)

FIG 5 Speed Canard Wing Test - Test Rig (schematically)

b. Results

All points of the test program were fulfilled completely. No damage propagation occurred. Fatigue damages of the composite structure were not detected. A static strength test hot/wet up to 160% limit load was successfully carried out after 3 simulated lives.

Then large manufacturing defects (two weak bondings between the wing shell and the spar flange over a length of 200 mm on the upper and lower sides of the wing) were caused. With these damages the wing failed at 100% limit load. The test fulfilled completely the certification requirements of the German and American certification authorities.

B. Grob G115-Wing

a. Test Description

This test served, as did the one for the Speed Canard wing, to determine the static strength, the fatigue life, the residual strength and the damage tolerance behaviour. The essential difference consisted in the fact that the G115 wing spar has a GFC flange and Nomex honeycomb core in the wing shell and the Speed Canard has a CFC flange and PVC foam in the wing shell. The fatigue life test for the G115 wing was run hot/wet, whilst it was run RT/dry for the Speed Canard wing. A total of 20 service damages and manufacturing defects were tested under static and fatigue loading. Figure 6 shows schematically the test set-up.

The following test sequence were carried out:

- manufacturing defects and impact damages inflicted
- conditioning of the wing at 45 °C/85% relative humidity for 2400 hours
- static test up to limit load at RT and 72 °C
- fatigue test for one life (12.000 simulated flight hours) with a random test load program (43 load cycles per flight hour) at RT with 6 temperature cycles of 72 °C; all loads of the fatigue program are factored by 1.1
- static test up to ultimate load at RT and 72 °C
- fatigue test for two further lives at RT with 12 temperature cycles of 72 °C (total 36.000 flight hours)
- static test up to ultimate load at RT
- static strength test up to failure at 72 °C

FIG 6 Grob G115 Wing Test - Test Rig (schematically)

b. Results

All points in the test programme were fulfilled. No propagation occurred at the damages caused during static and fatigue loading. For the static qualification close to ultimate load small damages (crippling) in the upper wing skin at 72 °C test temperature occur which, however, have no influence on the static load bearing capability of the wing.

Small fatigue damages occurred at the shear devices (root rib) during the fatigue life simulation. These damages were caused by the wing bearing being too stiff. After a modification to the bearing only a small propagation occurred to the damages. A repair of the damage was not necessary, all the following tests, including the residual strength test, were carried out with this damage without it ever becoming critical.

After the successful fatigue test and the following static test up to ultimate load at RT, the residual strength test at 72 °C shows a spar failure at 189% of limit load.

The test thus fulfilled all the certification requirements of the West German and American certification authorities. The Grob G115 aircraft received its FAA certification in December 1988.

SUMMARY

The small aircraft developed entirely in composite materials using LPC technology revealed very good damage tolerance behaviour in the technological structure investigation.

An operational and fatigue life of 12.000 flight hours was proved without any problem. The static strength in critical environmental conditions came up to expectations, and it was taken into consideration for the stress analysis. The technological investigations showed that the static load behaviour was influenced negatively but within acceptable limits by environmental factors (temperature and humidity). Influence due to environmental conditions on fatigue life could not be determined.

REFERENCES

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